

Financing Noncommunicable Disease Care in Rwanda: Assessing the Responsiveness of Community-Based Health Insurance to Chronic Health Needs

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Abstract

Background:

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are growing as major cause of death worldwide, disproportionately impacting low-and-middle income countries (LMICs). Although chronic illnesses are becoming more prevalent in Rwanda, the country's health financing system is still centered around acute and infectious care. This study examines whether Community-Based Health Insurance (CBHI) and Performance based Financing (PBF), Rwanda's flagship financing mechanisms are well positioned to provide long-term NCD care in the context of universal health coverage (UHC)

Methods:

The study used a mixed-methods approach, combining a narrative evaluation of peer reviewed and grey literature with secondary analysis of national mortality and finance data from 2023-2024. The analysis assessed how Rwanda's CBHI and PBF models matched the requirements for chronic disease care, as well as the burden of NCDs by age and data source.

Results:

Findings show that in Rwanda, NCDs are responsible for 59.3% of fatalities reported by the community and 47.7% of deaths recorded in facilities. Despite a nationwide expansion, CBHI coverage is still insufficient for chronic care, with minimal coverage for lifelong drugs and diagnostics. PBF incentives provide little assistance for managing NCDs and instead favor short-term, volume based treatments. Integrated chronic care is challenged by structural misalignment between CBHI and PBF, which disproportionately affect low-income and rural populations.

Conclusion:

The structure of health financing in Rwanda is still out of step with the country's changing disease burden. Restructuring financing methods to include chronic care and preventive treatments, modifying actuarial models, and implementing NCD specific performance incentives are all

necessary to meet the mounting issues associated with NCDs. Rwanda has the chance to set an example for adapting UHC frameworks to the realities of chronic care in LMICs thanks to its solid policy base it has.

Keywords: Non-communicable diseases, health financing, community-based health insurance, performance-based financing, universal health coverage, health policy, LMICs

1. Introduction

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are among one of the most pressing global health challenges of the 21st century(1). As of 2023, NCDs accounted for 41 million deaths annually equivalent to 74% of all global deaths. NCDs such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, cancer, and chronic respiratory illnesses are not only widespread but are increasingly and mainly concentrated in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs)(2). The listed four groups of diseases account for 80% of all premature NCD deaths. In LMICs, as of now there are 41 million deaths from NCDs each year, but this number is expected to rise to 52 million deaths annually by 2030, with LMICs bearing more than 75% of this toll and over 85% of premature deaths. Yet, despite the scale of their impact, NCDs remain chronically underfunded, receiving just 1% to 2% of development assistance for health (DAH), a clear mismatch between global disease burden and financial prioritization (3).

Beyond the epidemiological and financial aspects, NCDs pose an unforeseen socioeconomic and equity crisis (4). They impose long-term suffering on individuals and families, which threatens national productivity, and burdens already fragile health systems (4). For patients in low-income settings, chronic conditions often translate into catastrophic out-of-pocket expenditures, pushing households into poverty, as the more health expenditure is done through out-of-pocket expenses, the more it has several severe consequences which pushes individuals and households into poverty(5). For the next two decades, NCDs are estimated to cause a global cumulative economic loss of \$47 trillion between 2011 and 2030 (6,7). These will result in a loss of productivity and health expenditure, threatening development gains, particularly in Africa (8). By acknowledging this, global frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have called for an integrated approach to NCDs within universal health coverage (UHC) agendas (9). However, in practice for many countries the progress has been slow.

Rwanda stands at a crucial stage in its health transition within this global transition. There has been a shifting trend where before Rwanda was primarily burdened by communicable diseases but now is experiencing a rapid shift toward non-communicable diseases (NCDs) (10). Below in Figure 1 shows that in 2024, NCD accounted for almost half (47.7%) of all health facility-recorded deaths in Rwanda more than communicable diseases (42.9%) and external causes (9.4%). This trend is supported by community-based death data which show that NCDs cause 59.3% of deaths (11).

Conditions such as hypertension, diabetes, cancer, and mental health disorders pose a significant threat to global health, but mainly in urban areas where unhealthy lifestyles, alcohol consumption, and obesity are increasing more (12).

Figure 1: Trends in Causes of Deaths in Rwanda, 2023-2024

In response to all these rising of NCDs, the Rwandan health system has taken different measures and policies to address the growing NCD burden. Different measures like public health campaigns, such as car-free days and school-based education on nutrition and exercise, show a national effort to promote healthy lifestyles. Moreover, Rwanda has built a special lane, inlaid with synthetic rubber and painted green in many places in the city as part of a project aimed at revolutionizing the sporting experience and promoting physical fitness (13). Furthermore, the decentralization of NCD services through the WHO PEN (Package of Essential Noncommunicable) and PEN-Plus frameworks has improved the availability of diagnosis and treatment at lower levels of care. In terms of policies, Rwanda's strong performance in tobacco control reducing national smoking prevalence from 13% to 7% demonstrates political will and effective implementation of preventive strategies.

Figure 2: Decentralization of NCDs management in Rwanda, (14)

Despite these efforts, some challenges persist: Rwanda's health financing architecture remains predominantly structured around the disease profile of the early 2000s, with a strong emphasis on maternal health, infectious diseases, and acute care. Community-Based Health Insurance (CBHI) and Performance-Based Financing (PBF), Rwanda's two flagship health financing mechanisms, have been instrumental in achieving high service coverage, improved quality, and financial protection (15). Yet, their readiness to sustainably finance long-term NCD care remains unproven.

This paper explores whether CBHI and PBF are adequately structured, financed, and incentivized to respond to Rwanda's shifting disease burden. It examines the alignment (or misalignment) between Rwanda's financing tools and the growing demand for chronic care services. By analyzing the architecture, coverage, and incentive structures of both models, we seek to identify critical policy and design gaps and propose actionable recommendations to reposition Rwanda's financing strategies to meet the demands of long-term NCD care within a sustainable UHC framework.

2. Review of Literature

The global conversation on health system financing has mainly talked and evolved in response to infectious diseases and maternal-child health priorities, especially in low-and-middle-income countries (LMICs). However, as NCDs become the leading cause of morbidity and mortality globally, the incapacity of current financing models to adequately handle chronic conditions has drawn more attention.

2.1 Global Financing Trends for NCDs

Despite accounting for over 74% of all global deaths, NCDs receive less than 2% of global development assistance for health (DAH), a figure that has not changed for quite some time. Given that over 85% of premature NCD deaths occur in LMICs, there's a mismatch between the disease burden and the financial prioritization of it. NCD pandemic levies a heavy toll on international finances where it was estimated from 2011 to 2015 that NCDs will drain over US\$ 50 trillion from the global economy [ref]. It has been proved from different studies that preventing NCDs is very cheap compared with the costs of staying in inaction. In LMICs, the WHO population level NCD "best buy" interventions cost less than US 0.20 per capita annually, while in middle-income nations the cost is less than US\$ 0.50. It would cost \$11.4 billion to scale up the best buys from 5% to 80% coverage in all LMICs, which is less than 5% of the current yearly health expenditure and nearly equal to the extreme cost of inaction (16).

In many countries the majority of the domestic health funding comes from the over-the counter payments account since patients pay for their own care as and when their expenses arise (17). In contrast to medical insurance, mostly known as pre-pooling, these so called "out-of-pocket" expenditures can be quite costly when it comes to chronic illness that necessitates continuous care with pricey medications (18). Out-of-pocket payments account for approximately 40% of all health expenditure in low-income countries and lower-income countries (19). Although NCDs have been the leading cause of mortality in recent years in most countries, in 2011 only half of WHO members states listed NCD line items in their health budgets(16). Even on where the funding for NCD exists, it is more often lumped into broader categories like primary healthcare or health system strengthening making it harder to track and evaluate. For instance, in 2015 out of the total US\$ 475 million in DAH for NCDs only \$128 million went to mental health and only \$41 million went to tobacco control (20). And nearly 20% of this total funding came from private foundations such as the Gates Foundation, but the majority of support remains insufficient and fragmented.

It is becoming more and more obvious that the NCD financing gap cannot be solved by relying on only external funding. In order to specifically prioritize NCDs, most countries will need to modify their public financing structures. Countries will continue to suffer with fragmented responses, delayed service delivery and poor health outcomes in the absence of consistent funding both locally and internationally.

2.2. The Rwandan Health System and Financing Evolution

Rwanda's health system has historically been recognized for its achievements in expanding access and improving outcomes through innovative financing mechanisms such as Community Based Health Insurance (CBHI) and Performance Based Financing (PBF). Different evaluations have been made and have shown that CBHI increased service utilization and financial protection while PBF significantly improved sectors like maternal and child health outcomes, institutional deliveries, and preventive service uptake (21,22).

However, in different literature, it reveals a clear gap: these financing mechanisms were designed primarily for acute and infectious care contexts (23). Whereas for instance, CBHI was built around a per capita contribution model with an emphasis on essential health services and user copayments. Similarly, PBF has largely rewarded providers that deal with volume-based services like immunizations, antenatal visits, and deliveries. Mostly on indicators that are aligned with the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) rather than the NCDs specific targets

Care for chronic diseases especially diabetes, hypertension and mental health is still not given enough priority in terms of design and financing as pointed out by a number of studies (24). While overall quality indicators were improving in general services, NCD specific metrics were still needed interventions (25).

There have been so many efforts like the WHO Global NCD Action Plan (2013-2020) and integration of NCD targets into Sustainable Development Goal 3 (target 3.4) and in 2015, a WHO expert consultant recommended strengthening domestic NCD financing through increased government allocations, introducing taxes on health harming products like tobacco and sugary drinks and innovating around financing mechanisms such as solidarity levies (26–28). Some countries have moved in this direction, but scale and sustainability remain concerns. Different authors have argued that the failure to financially integrate NCDs into universal health coverage (UHC) frameworks weakens both equity and long-term health system sustainability. In its core, NCDs require lifelong treatment, medication adherence and frequent follow-ups, and their financial requirements differ significantly from those episodic, short-term care models employed for infectious disease control (29).

2.3. Decentralization and Emerging NCD Care models

In recent years, In Rwanda we have seen a growing shift toward integrating NCD services into primary healthcare (PHC) system. Rwanda adopted the WHO PEN (Package of Essential Noncommunicable disease interventions), and PEN-Plus framework shows this transition [\[ref\]](#). Figure 2 shown above shows how these models promote task-shifting, decentralization of diagnostics and medication delivery, and the integration of NCD services at the health center and district hospital levels. Early evaluations that have been made show the increase in service availability; however, long-term sustainability remains uncertain without financing reform.

Moreover, evidence shows that Rwanda's strong health system governance has helped innovative public health campaigns to prevent NCDs such as car free days, smoking reduction policies where different new tax reforms where they increased excise duty on cigarettes, beer and other alcoholic beverages, but also Rwanda has built city infrastructures for physical fitness, but financing for chronic care treatment has not kept pace(10,30).

2.4. Identified gaps and rationale for current study

While in Rwanda there has been considerable strides in public health and primary care, different literatures show how its financing architecture is still primarily oriented towards communicable diseases. It is unclear how Rwanda's current financing instruments; CBHI and the PBF align with the rising demand for care for chronic NCDs. Most of the research to date has concentrated more on maternal and infectious care utilization and quality improvements, with little analysis on how effectively these models can support the range of care needed for NCDs.

This paper addresses this gap by examining whether Rwanda's CBHI and PBF mechanisms are structurally and operationally capable of supporting long-term integrated NCD care. By looking at the broader UHC and epidemiological transition framework, this paper is purposed to provide evidence-based recommendations for aligning financing strategies with Rwanda's evolving disease burden

3. Research Methodology

This study used a mixed-methods approach, where both secondary analysis and a narrative review of peer-reviewed and grey literature were used to assess the alignment of Rwanda's health financing architecture with the growing burden of non-communicable diseases (NCDs)

3.1. Data Sources

Several data sources were used as the primary source of information for the analysis. First, national health datasets obtained from the Rwanda Ministry of Health (MoH) were utilized particularly mortality data from the years 2023-2024. The datasets included disaggregated figures obtained from both community level surveillance systems and health facility-based reporting mechanisms, but specifically with a focus on non-communicable disease (NCD) categories such as cancer, diabetes, and other chronic conditions. Second, health financing documents and reports that were published by the MOH and affiliated national agencies were used and reviewed. Which these provided insights to the recent budgetary allocations and the operational structure of Rwanda's two major health financing mechanisms which is the community-based health insurance (CBHI) scheme and the Performance-based financing (PBF) system. Finally, the study included also a review of peer-reviewed academic literature and global health financing reports. In these reports, we included data on the development assistance for health (DAH), global and regional economic impacts of NCDs and the implementation status of global interventions such as the WHO "Best Buys" and PEN/PEN-Plus strategies.

3.2. Analytical Framework

The study was guided by three main analytical pillars. First, we assessed the burden of NCDs by computing age-specific mortality rates (per 100,000 population) using national data from the Ministry of Health. This data included figures for cancer, diabetes, and other chronic conditions, disaggregated by source, community reported deaths versus those captured in health facilities. These patterns were then visualized using python's Matplotlib and Seaborn libraries to reveal trends and potential reporting discrepancies. Second, we analyzed how well Rwanda's current health financing mechanisms align with the demands of chronic care. This included an assessment of budgetary allocation, structural design, and incentive mechanisms under community Based Health Insurance (CBHI), and Performance Based Financing (PBF), focusing whether these schemes are equipped to support the long-term nature of NCD management. Lastly the findings were contextualized through a review of existing global and regional literature to know the Rwanda's experience within the broader trend and context in NCD financing and identify areas of alignment or divergence from international best practices.

4. Results and Discussion

Burden of NCDs by Age and Source

From the analysis of the Rwanda Ministry of Health mortality data from 2023-2024 shows a rising and concerning burden of NCDs, especially particular among older age groups. When you look at different NCDs such as cancers, diabetes, and other NCDs, mortality rates increase significantly with age and there are majority of deaths recorded through community-based and health facility-reporting systems. Look at figures 3a below shows that cancer related mortality is at 611.5 per 100,000 in the community and 72.8 per 100,000 in facilities among individuals that are aged 80 and above. Figure 3b below also shows that diabetes mortality increases with age as well, reaching 272.6 per 100,000 in the community and 22.0 per 100,000 in the facility data for people aged 75-79. Furthermore, in the mortality rate from various NCDs (such as respiratory and cardiovascular conditions) rises overtime to 274.4 per 100,000 in the community data and 184.2 per 100,000 in facilities among the oldest age group (Figure 3c)

Figure 3a: Cancer mortality rate per 100,000 by age group

Figure 3b: Diabetes mortality rate per 100,000 by age group

Figure 3c: Other NCDs mortality rate per 100,000 by age group

As presented earlier in **figure 1**, NCDs now account for 47.7% of all facility deaths and for the community deaths 59.3% surpassing infectious diseases. How this epidemiological transition is, is not matched by the shift in financing priorities. Current financing continues to heavily focus more on infectious diseases although it is also necessary through earmarked donor funding and indicator-linked domestic spending

CBHI and NCD Coverage Gaps

CBHI, locally known as Mutuelle de Sante, covers approximately 91% of the population. Its functions are through a tiered payment system that is based on socioeconomic classification (Ubudehe), with full subsidies for the poorest households. The CBHI coverage has increased from 2015 being 75.4% to over 91% in 2023 as shown in the figure 4 below that shows the growth trajectory in the CBHI coverage at the national level.

Figure 4: CBHI Coverage in Rwanda, 2015-2023

While CBHI has reduced out-of-pocket expenditures for acute care and maternal health challenges remain. Out of pocket costs persist for the treatments and diagnosis for chronic NCDs, creating access barriers. The financing package under CBHI does not fully integrate preventive and long-term management services necessary for NCDs.

There are different gaps that have occurred in this, where there is inadequate coverage; meaning lifelong medications such as; insulin, antihypertensives, but also cancer therapies, and diagnostic tests are not consistently covered. Moreover, there is a cost-sharing burden where co-payments and annual ceilings often deter patients from seeking regular follow-up or adhering to long-term treatment. Furthermore, there's a design bias where the scheme's actuarial assumptions are based on short-term service utilization models, limiting its flexibility to accommodate chronic conditions.

These gaps are really concerning given that patients who have NCD related require continuous care, medication adherence, and diagnostic monitoring over years or decades.

Furthermore, CBHI coverage rates are not uniform across the country. District level data for 2023 shows the disparities, as shown in **figure 5** below. Inequities in NCD patients' access to different services and financial protection may be made worse by these differences in the geographic coverage. As the burden of NCDs continue to rise across all age groups, districts that has low coverage may be burdened with both unmet healthcare requirements and limited financial protection

Figure 5: CBHI Coverage Rate by District (2023-2024)

PBF and NCD Service Incentives

The Rwanda’s PBF model has improved the utilization and quality mainly in maternal and child health services, with different indicators tied to performance-based payments. But the format naturally encourages quantifiable, short-term results (31). Current PBF metrics do not adequately reflect NCD care, which requires behavioral counseling, multidisciplinary inputs, and ongoing monitoring. For example, hypertension control, diabetes follow-up, and cancer screening there are few or no incentives for them. This has several negative consequences where facilities deprioritize NCD services because they generate no additional revenue, this gives providers to incentivize to focus more on the short-term measurable outcomes rather than the chronic disease management. The absence of including NCDs in PBF limits or gives the mismatch between Rwanda’s disease burden and its financial model.

Structural Misalignment between CBHI and PBF

Ideally, CBHI and PBF should collaborate more, with PBF driving service quality and CBHI ensuring financial access. However, both programs focus more on acute and episodic care. Their synergy is reduced in the absence of NCD-specific incentives or benefit coverage.

This could mean that facilities with high CBHI enrollment could treat more chronic patients but lack the PBF incentive to do so, but it could also imply that providers delivering long-term care are not getting rewards unless those services are part of the indicator dashboard.

This misalignment in policy prevents the realization for integrated and strategic purchasing for chronic disease care.

Implications for Equity and Health System Design

All the findings that we presented shows a fundamental misalignment between Rwanda's growing burden of disease and its current health financing architecture. While CBHI has improved the overall access to care in Rwanda, it has not been adequately restructured to handle the chronic and cumulative nature of NCD management. People with NCDs confront ongoing financial obstacles that could postpone therapy, lower adherence, and ultimately worsen outcomes if they do not have full coverage for necessary prescription drugs, diagnostic tests and routine follow-ups.

Rwanda is not the only country that is facing this difficulty. Most low-and-middle-income countries are having difficulty adjusting their health finance models to meet the long-term needs of NCD care, according to a growing literature. The Lancet NCDI Poverty Commission (2020) claims that chronic illnesses are often neglected and overlooked by underfunded public insurance schemes resulting in structural undercoverage for low-income groups (32). In a similar way, WHO (2018) pointed out that for the Universal health coverage initiatives to be equitable and long-lasting, NCD prevention and management must be strongly integrated (33).

Without full coverage for necessary prescription drugs, diagnostic tests, and routine checkups, people with noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) in Rwanda have ongoing financial burden that could postpone treatment, lower adherence to treatment, and eventually worsen results (34). Different studies like Lu et al. (2012) and Wagstaff et al. (2016) also show how even a small or a minor co-payment can have disproportionate impact on the poor's health seeking behavior, particularly when it comes to illnesses that need lifelong care (35,36).

In addition to being technical inefficiencies, these funding gaps represent equitable difficulties. Rural communities and lower-income households, who depend largely on CBHI and have the least ability to pay for uncovered treatments out of pocket, are disproportionately affected (37). Inequality in this case could worsen and Rwanda's health gains could be undone if health financing is not restructured as the burden of disease moves toward NCDs (38).

Rwanda however has a solid foundation upon on which to keep building on. Restructuring benefit packages for NCDs can take advantage of the institutional and political momentum that allowed for the quick development of CBHI and the success of maternal-child health. It would be possible to greatly expand the coverage, lower catastrophic health costs and promote long-term population health by bringing Rwanda's health financing model into line with the international best practices, such as WHO PEN/Plus model, which places an emphasis on decentralized chronic care

Future changes should definitely consist of:

- Adding necessary preventative diagnostic, and chronic pharmaceutical services to the CBHI insurance package
- Actuarial models should be updated to account for long-term service requirements as opposed to acute care situations
- Incorporating digital health monitoring to help with chronic condition care continuity
- Putting equity first by focusing outreach and funding on districts with high NCD burdens and low CBHI coverage

By applying this, Rwanda can improve its universal health care model and guarantee that no one is left behind in the changing health landscape by readjusting financial protection to reflect the realities of chronic diseases.

5. Conclusion

This study analysis shows that Rwanda's current health financing structure and its changing epidemiological profile are seriously out of sync. Although Rwanda has made great progress in increase the health coverage through different programs like the Community Based Health Insurance (CBHI), the system has not fully equipped to meet the long-term demand for noncommunicable disease (NCD) management. According to the 2023-2024 mortality data that were reported in the community and facility based, noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) are currently the main cause of death. However, the current financing model promotes acute care and has structural limitations that hinder its ability to support the management of chronic diseases.

Financial vulnerability for people with NCDs is made worse by significantly coverage constraints, such as the exclusion or partial reimbursement of necessary diagnostics and prescriptions, co-payment requirements, and actuarial models based on short-term service utilization (39). Despite almost universal insurance coverage in the nation, these disparities disproportionately impact rural and lower-income groups, worsening already existing health inequities.

Rwanda has a solid foundation for adaption thanks to its past achievement in implementing different health reforms (40). Future changes though, must specifically address how to pay for chronic care services. To guarantee that the system is both equitable and sustainable, it is imperative that comprehensive NCD coverage be incorporated into CBHI benefit packages, reimbursement plans be modified, and long-term finance models be improved.

Furthermore, Rwanda offers a useful case study for other low-and middle-income countries going through same transitions, especially in light of the rising international agreement on the

significance of NCD investment. It is essential to strategically reorganize the domestic financial structures in accordance with international guidelines like the WHO “Best Buys” and PEN –Plus initiatives in order to reduce the negative effects of inaction on the economy and public health.

References

1. WHO. Noncommunicable diseases [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2025 Jul 30]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/noncommunicable-diseases>
2. The World Bank. Delivering Primary Care for Non-communicable Diseases: A Compendium of Service Delivery Models in Low and Middle-income Countries [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jul 30]. Available from: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/bitstreams/ceba27c4-b6b6-4933-9b00-a737dd462bba/download>
3. NCD Alliance. Financing NCDs [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jul 30]. Available from: <https://ncdalliance.org/explore-ncds/solutions/financing-ncds>
4. Havard School of public health. The Global Economic Burden of Non-communicable Diseases [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jul 30]. Available from: https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Harvard_HE_GlobalEconomicBurdenNonCommunicableDiseases_2011.pdf
5. Sirag A, Mohamed Nor N. Out-of-Pocket Health Expenditure and Poverty: Evidence from a Dynamic Panel Threshold Analysis. *Healthcare*. 2021 May 3;9(5):536.
6. Chen S, Kuhn M, Prettner K, Bloom DE. The macroeconomic burden of noncommunicable diseases in the United States: Estimates and projections. Husain MJ, editor. *PLoS ONE*. 2018 Nov 1;13(11):e0206702.
7. Ipinnimo TM, Elegbede OE, Durowade KA, Adewoye KR, Ibirongbe DO, Ajayi PO, et al. Cost of illness of non-communicable diseases in private and public health facilities in Nigeria: a qualitative and quantitative approach. *Pan Afr Med J* [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2025 Jul 30];44. Available from: <https://www.panafrican-med-journal.com/content/article/44/6/full>
8. Akintunde TS, Akintunde AA, Adeomi AA. Economic burden and psycho-social implications of Non- Communicable Diseases on adults and their households in South-west Nigeria. *Ann Health Res*. 2018 Dec 9;4(2):97–107.
9. Collins TE, Akselrod S, Atun R, Bennett S, Ogbuoji O, Hanson M, et al. Converging global health agendas and universal health coverage: financing whole-of-government action through UHC+. *The Lancet Global Health*. 2023 Dec;11(12):e1978–85.

10. Rwanda Biomedical Center. Rwanda Intensifies Fight Against Non-Communicable Diseases [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2025 Jul 30]. Available from: [https://rbc.gov.rw/wp/rwanda-intensifies-fight-against-non-communicable-diseases/#:~:text=As%20non%2Dcommunicable%20diseases%20\(NCDs,initiatives%20aimed%20at%20combating%20NCDs](https://rbc.gov.rw/wp/rwanda-intensifies-fight-against-non-communicable-diseases/#:~:text=As%20non%2Dcommunicable%20diseases%20(NCDs,initiatives%20aimed%20at%20combating%20NCDs)
11. National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda. Non-Communicable Diseases Become the Leading Cause of Death in Rwanda. 2025 Apr 30; Available from: <https://www.statistics.gov.rw/news-and-events/Non-Communicable-Diseases-Become-the-Leading-Cause-of-Death-in-Rwanda#:~:text=Kigali%2C%20April%202025%20%E2%80%94%20The%20Rwanda,reported%20data%2C%20but%20Clear%20Trends>
12. Garg RK. The alarming rise of lifestyle diseases and their impact on public health: A comprehensive overview and strategies for overcoming the epidemic. *Journal of Research in Medical Sciences* [Internet]. 2025 Jan [cited 2025 Jul 30];30(1). Available from: https://journals.lww.com/10.4103/jrms.jrms_54_24
13. John Kalii. City of Kigali unveils rubber-padded running track in boost to fitness. 2023 Jun 19 [cited 2025 Jul 30]; Available from: <https://www.citizen.digital/news/city-of-kigali-unveils-rubber-padded-running-track-in-boost-to-fitness-n321954>
14. Kerry Cullinan. <https://www.citizen.digital/news/city-of-kigali-unveils-rubber-padded-running-track-in-boost-to-fitness-n321954>. 2025 Feb 26 [cited 2025 Jul 30]; Available from: <https://healthpolicy-watch.news/in-rwanda-decentralised-health-coverage-starts-with-community-health-workers/>
15. International Labor Office. Progress towards Universal Health Coverage [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jul 30]. Available from: https://www.social-protection.org/gimi/gess/Media.action;jsessionid=aKJb3Qx0kNHQong5yo7MDfd_6Jm12PYyUSpx9IrCUucN9Mz2eu3s!-422788549?id=15435#:~:text=Figure%203.&text=Source:%20World%20Bank%2C%202016.,the%20total%20cost%20of%20treatment
16. Allen LN. Financing national non-communicable disease responses. *Global Health Action*. 2017 Jan;10(1):1326687.
17. The World Bank. Financing Health Services; in Developing Countries [Internet]. 1987. Available from: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/468091468137379607/pdf/multi-page.pdf>
18. Eze P, Ilechukwu S, Lawani LO. Impact of community-based health insurance in low- and middle-income countries: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Vojnov L, editor. PLoS ONE*. 2023 Jun 27;18(6):e0287600.
19. Bolongaita S, Lee Y, Johansson KA, Haaland ØA, Tolla MT, Lee J, et al. Financial hardship associated with catastrophic out-of-pocket spending tied to primary care services in low- and

- lower-middle-income countries: findings from a modeling study. *BMC Med.* 2023 Sep 14;21(1):356.
20. Nugent R. A Chronology of Global Assistance Funding for NCD. *gh.* 2016 Dec 1;11(4):371.
 21. Paul Gertler, Christel Vermeersch. Using Performance Incentives to Improve Health Outcomes. 2012 Jun 1 [cited 2025 Jul 31]; Available from: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2089240
 22. Basinga P, Gertler PJ, Binagwaho A, Soucat AL, Sturdy J, Vermeersch CM. Effect on maternal and child health services in Rwanda of payment to primary health-care providers for performance: an impact evaluation. *The Lancet.* 2011 Apr;377(9775):1421–8.
 23. Hanson K, Brikci N, Erlangga D, Alebachew A, De Allegri M, Balabanova D, et al. The Lancet Global Health Commission on financing primary health care: putting people at the centre. *The Lancet Global Health.* 2022 May;10(5):e715–72.
 24. NCD Alliance. Call for simultaneous action on diabetes and hypertension for more resilient health systems [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jul 31]. Available from: <https://idf.org/media/uploads/2023/05/attachments-24.pdf>
 25. MINISANTE. National Strategy and Costed Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of Non-Communicable Diseases in Rwanda [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2025 Jul 31]. Available from: https://www.moh.gov.rw/fileadmin/user_upload/Moh/Publications/Strategic_Plan/Rwanda_National_NCD_Strategy_Costed_Action_Plan_FINAL_12072021.pdf
 26. Dr Guy Fones. How to sustainably finance the noncommunicable diseases and mental health response [Internet]. WHO; 2025 [cited 2025 Jul 31]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/commentaries/detail/how-to-sustainably-finance-the-noncommunicable-diseases-and-mental-health-response#:~:text=For%20essential%20NCD%20and%20mental,action%20across%20regions%20and%20countries.>
 27. WHO. GLOBAL ACTION PLAN FOR THE PREVENTION AND CONTROL OF NONCOMMUNICABLE DISEASES 2013-2020 [Internet]. 2013 [cited 2025 Jul 31]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241506236>
 28. WHO. SDG Target 3.4 | Noncommunicable diseases and mental health: By 2030, reduce by one third premature mortality from non-communicable diseases through prevention and treatment and promote mental health and well-being [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/topics/indicator-groups/indicator-group-details/GHO/sdg-target-3.4-noncommunicable-diseases-and-mental-health>
 29. Paremoer L. Universal Health Coverage for Non-communicable Diseases and Health Equity: Reflections on the Role of Ideas and Democratic Decision-Making; Comment on “Universal Health Coverage for Non-Communicable Diseases and Health Equity: Lessons from Australian Primary Healthcare.” *Int J Health Policy Manag.* 2021 Aug 30;1.

30. Naphtal Hakizimana. Impact of Cigarette Excise Rate Increases on Tobacco Consumption and Tax Revenue for Rwanda [Internet]. 2018 [cited 2025 Jul 31]. Available from: https://www.rra.gov.rw/fileadmin/user_upload/impact_of_cigarette_excise_rate_increases_on_tobacco_consumption_and_tax_revenue_final.pdf
31. Ndayishimiye C, Nduwayezu R, Sowada C, Dubas-Jakóbczyk K. Performance-based financing in Rwanda: a qualitative analysis of healthcare provider perspectives. *BMC Health Serv Res.* 2025 Mar 22;25(1):418.
32. Bukhman G, Mocumbi AO, Atun R, Becker AE, Bhutta Z, Binagwaho A, et al. The Lancet NCDI Poverty Commission: bridging a gap in universal health coverage for the poorest billion. *The Lancet.* 2020 Oct;396(10256):991–1044.
33. Fisher M, Freeman T, Mackean T, Friel S, Baum F. Universal Health Coverage for Non-communicable Diseases and Health Equity: Lessons From Australian Primary Healthcare. *Int J Health Policy Manag.* 2020 Nov 23;1.
34. Kerry Cullinan. NCD Advocates Mobilise in Rwanda Ahead of UN High-Level Meeting. 2025 Feb 13 [cited 2025 Jul 31]; Available from: <https://healthpolicy-watch.news/ncd-advocates-mobilise-in-rwanda-ahead-of-un-high-level-meeting/>
35. Lu C, Chin B, Lewandowski JL, Basinga P, Hirschhorn LR, Hill K, et al. Towards Universal Health Coverage: An Evaluation of Rwanda Mutuelles in Its First Eight Years. Postma M, editor. *PLoS ONE.* 2012 Jun 18;7(6):e39282.
36. Wagstaff, Adam. Social health insurance reexamined [Internet]. 2007 [cited 2025 Jul 31]. Available from: <https://ideas.repec.org/p/wbk/wbrwps/4111.html>
37. Nyandekwe M, Nzayirambaho M, Kakoma JB. Universal health insurance in Rwanda: major challenges and solutions for financial sustainability case study of Rwanda community-based health insurance part I. *Pan Afr Med J* [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2025 Jul 31];37. Available from: <https://www.panafrican-med-journal.com/content/article/37/55/full>
38. Barasa E, Kazungu J, Nguhiu P, Ravishankar N. Examining the level and inequality in health insurance coverage in 36 sub-Saharan African countries. *BMJ Glob Health.* 2021 Apr;6(4):e004712.
39. Shigeoka H. The Effect of Patient Cost-Sharing on Utilization, Health and Risk Protection. *SSRN Journal* [Internet]. 2012 [cited 2025 Jul 31]; Available from: <http://www.ssrn.com/abstract=2174740>
40. WHO. Strengthening health systems to further improve the population's health and well-being.

